

Social Media in Language Learning: Implications for Second Language Motivation and Linguistic Acquisition: a Comprehensive Review

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Communication,
Cultures, Foreign
Languages, Skills, Social
Media

Received : 20, August

Revised : 18, September

Accepted: 18, October

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ABSTRACT

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the effects of social media on language acquisition, with a particular focus on the use of social media as instruments for developing language skills and as venues for intercultural dialogue. The first aspect under consideration is to the possible impact of social media as instruments for developing language skills, including reading and writing, as well as listening and speaking abilities. The first examines the role of social media as cross-cultural interaction channels in enhancing pragmatic socioeconomic skills and second language (L2) motivation, while the latter specifically investigates the potential implications of social media on these aspects. The findings suggest that social media offers several advantages and serves various purposes in the language learning processes. These include the availability of genuine input materials, the provision of less anxiety-inducing practice environments, a plethora of chances for intercultural dialogue, and the promotion of learner cooperation. The research further underscores possible limits associated with social networking platforms, such as issues over distraction and contradicting information. Finally, several potential avenues for further empirical investigation have been suggested.

INTRODUCTION

The rise and exponential expansion of social media has garnered significant interest from scholars in the field of second language acquisition. They have served as a catalyst for several research endeavors aimed at investigating the potential of social media as pedagogical instruments. Indeed, a growing corpus of research spanning several disciplines, viewpoints, and approaches has been undertaken, with valuable conclusions. In this regard, it is important to construct a comprehensive synthesis in order to critically examine the existing body of knowledge, consolidate the findings that have been derived, and identify areas that need further investigation. To provide more clarity, this scholarly article aims to address two primary research inquiries: the effects of social media as instruments for developing language abilities in the context of language learning, and the effects of social media as platforms for intercultural contact on language learning. The relevance of these two study issues lies in the widely acknowledged understanding that language learning encompasses the acquisition of linguistic information as well as the development of intercultural competence (Jin, S. (2015). Through a comprehensive examination of relevant literature, the present study endeavors to ascertain noteworthy discoveries, establish instructional implications for educators and learners alike, and provide theoretical recommendations that will guide subsequent studies as well as practical application

METHODOLOGY

A number of activities related to library data collection techniques make up library research. The term "library research" refers to research that makes use of existing resources found in libraries, such as books, magazines, papers, historical narratives, or pure literature relevant to the topic of study.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The effects of social media platforms on individuals

A Brief Explanation of Social Media

Kaplan and Heinlein (2010) conducted a research aiming to provide a definition for social media. They describe social media as a collection of internet-based apps that are built upon the principles and technology advancements of Web 2.0. These applications enable users to generate and share content amongst them. Social media is often seen as a comprehensive word including several sub-genres. In their work, Kaplan and Haenlein present a comprehensive framework consisting of six distinct categories of social media platforms. These categories encompass blogs, such as Wordpress, social networking sites like Facebook and MySpace, virtual game worlds such as World of Warcraft, virtual social worlds like Second Life, content communities exemplified by YouTube, and collaborative projects such as Wikipedia. In order to get a thorough comprehension, this research aims to align with Kaplan and Hoenlein's categorization in the subsequent review.

*The Utilization of Social Media as Tools for Enhancing Language Learning
Literacy Skills: Reading and Writing*

Communication instruction and acquisition academics are now investigating the impact of social media on language training, specifically in relation to various language abilities. It is worth mentioning that several research have examined the possible roles of social media in providing help in different aspects of writing and reading. Previous study on the improvement of writing skills via the use of social media has mostly focused on empirical investigations of writing fluency, writing quality, and self-efficacy in writing.

As stated by Lannin (2007), Writing fluency is often defined as the degree of cohesion and coherence shown in written expression. In other words, the process of generating ideas significantly contributes to the improvement of writing fluency. Vikneswaran and Krish conducted a case study to investigate the potential benefits of incorporating Facebook into official writing training. They observed that students often struggle to generate cohesive written work due to feelings of nervousness and a lack of ideas. The research findings indicate that Facebook has the potential to provide several advantages in the realm of improving writing skills. Stapa et al. (year) highlighted the significance of students' statements on the enhancement of their writing fluency via engaging in debates of ideas on private group sites, as seen in the gathered interview data. In other words, social media platforms have the potential to provide help to language learners by offering collaborative writing spaces where they may engage in activities such as brainstorming, composing, and revising their views. This finding is consistent with the research conducted by Alberth (2019), which posits that authors, when situated in an online environment, have the ability to enhance their idea generation process by using diverse web-based resources.

Shih, R. C. (2011). Asserts that the implementation of a longitudinal study for a writing program utilizing Facebook reveals that this platform effectively facilitates interactions between authors and readers. Additionally, it enables students to evaluate and provide feedback on their peers' written works, thereby affording learners the chance to make revisions to their own compositions. Consequently, this process contributes to the enhancement of various aspects of writing quality, including grammar, structure, content, organization, and word choice. Similarly, Wichadee , S. (2013) conducted a study to investigate the impact of peer feedback in a writing class that used Facebook as a platform, specifically focusing on its role in improving the quality of writing. He claimed that peer feedback plays a crucial role in enhancing the writing proficiency of learners. The author argues that students are aware that their work will be evaluated by readers, which prompts them to exercise more caution and precision in the composition process.

Regarding self-efficacy in writing, it is important to acknowledge that self-efficacy pertains to an individual's beliefs in their ability to successfully do

a certain task and has a strong positive association with confidence. Bandura (1997) and Raoofi, Tan, and Chan (2012) are two authors whose works have been referenced. The user's text is incomplete and does not provide any information. Prior research has shown that some individuals engaged in language learning have a lack of confidence as a result of their restricted linguistic abilities, particularly when it comes to presenting their work to a wider audience. Prichard (2013) conducted a study. One potential solution to this issue is the use of social media into the teaching of writing. According to the research conducted by Vikneswaran and Krish, it has been observed that social media sites, like Facebook, have a grammar checker feature that automatically rectifies writing mistakes made by language learners. Consequently, pupils have a heightened sense of ease while engaging in the act of writing, as they are relieved of any concerns or anxieties

The topic of discussion pertains to the subjects of grammar and vocabulary. Vikneswaran, T. and Krish, P. (2016). Furthermore, Nishioka performed a qualitative research study with the aim of investigating the impact of a social-media-enhanced teaching program in a Japanese writing class. The findings suggest that students were inspired to engage in writing activities due to the presence of native speakers and real readers on the social media site. The students' confidence and motivation to write were enhanced as a result of their perception that native speakers shown a sincere interest in reading their written work. The article authored by Nishioka (2020) is of academic nature.

Despite the extensive body of research performed on the effects of social media on language acquisition skills, there remains a scarcity of empirical studies specifically examining its influence on reading abilities.

Solmaz, O. (2018). In a study done by Kabilan et al., it was found that the results obtained from a survey indicate that reading material from social media platforms typically enhances learners' desire to read. Additionally, a significant number of learners said that engaging in online reading activities via these platforms had a positive impact on their reading abilities. Kabilan et al (2010)

Although Kabilan et al.'s investigation failed to give a detailed explanation of the specific aspect of reading skills that they developed, Abdullah's more recent exploratory research suggests that social media platforms offer learners a diverse range of texts and information. Consequently, this exposure may potentially enhance reading skills, such as skimming (Abdullah, 2019).

Oral Communication Skills

Despite a lack of extensive research on the impact of social media on language learners' speaking skills, there is a noticeable increase in the number of studies using various methodologies in this area. Many of them, particularly, investigate the educational opportunities provided by social media as platforms for sharing information.

As stated by Brown (1994), the act of speaking is considered a reactive process in which information is both received and produced. According to Namaziandost and Nasri, the development of speaking skills in conventional English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes is challenging due to the need for students to possess not just sufficient language talents, but also the ability to establish social relationships for effective communication.

With the primary concern in consideration, the researchers examined social networking sites as a prospective solution and began a survey for investigation. The self-reported data emphasizes the use of social media as a tool for practice. According to the findings, it can be inferred that a majority of students hold the belief that engaging in conversations with native speakers via internet-based platforms serves as a source of motivation, leading to enhanced practice and improvement in their speaking skill (Namaziandost & Nasri, 2019).

Additionally, claims that the acquisition of speaking abilities has always been a challenge for English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) learners due to the fact that English does not form an integral part of their everyday life. The individual posits that social media platforms, such as Skype, YouTube, and WhatsApp, provide sufficient means of connecting with other English speakers and significant opportunity for practice, thereby potentially addressing the existing deficiency. The analysis of the experimental data supports the conclusion that each of the three social media platforms have a positive impact on the improvement of learners' speaking abilities. It has been observed that there has been a noticeable improvement in learners' oral outputs with regards to content, word use, grammatical correctness, and fluency. One can question the ways in which YouTube, as a versatile platform, contributes to the development of learners' speaking skills. Indeed, this phenomenon may be somewhat elucidated by a research conducted by Ilyas and Putri, which was experiment-based in nature. The researchers claim that using YouTube as a platform for language acquisition enables students to enhance their speaking skills via the process of repetition. In this context, pupils have developed an increased sense of self-assurance while engaging in oral communication, since they are able to do so without being too concerned about making errors. Ilyas, M., and Putri, M. E. (2020). Likewise, the acquisition of listening skills is considered challenging, particularly in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) settings. Numerous research have endeavored to investigate if social media may serve as a means to enhance listening motivation and facilitate the development of listening skills.

Silviyanti, T. M. (2014) conducted a study on the impact of incorporating YouTube videos into listening classes on students' motivation to learn. The researcher utilized a combination of open and closed questionnaires to assess students' views regarding YouTube-assisted listening classes. The findings revealed that a significant number of students expressed a belief that the inclusion of YouTube videos in listening classes enhanced their motivation and interest. This was attributed to the ability to observe native speakers' conversational style and mannerisms.

Additionally, it is worth noting that YouTube offers sufficient audio-visual resources to assist students who may have lower proficiency levels in

comprehending the subject matter, hence reducing their levels of learning-related anxiety. The citation provided is in the correct format for an academic reference. Another study conducted by Dirjal, A. H., et al (2020) to investigate the possible impact of Skype on the development of listening motivation and listening abilities. The discovery demonstrates that by providing a realistic communication setting, such as an immediate discussion between individuals, Skype assists learners in overcoming language anxiety and so enhances their ability to engage in listening practice.

Ayu, L. P. (2016) researched to a comprehensive literature review to synthesize existing ideas and studies on the effects of YouTube videos on listening instruction, with the aim of enhancing listening abilities. As a result, Ayu identified and concluded numerous advantages associated with using YouTube videos in teaching listening. Specifically, by providing students with access to genuine resources, students are afforded the opportunity to critically examine and acquire both content-based knowledge and language proficiency. For instance, with the use of multimedia tools and video-text, learners have the ability to deduce the meaning of words and speech they have heard, while simultaneously acquiring knowledge of the subject matter. Furthermore, Mayoral et al. (year) conducted a study that examined the use of YouTube in a formal language education context. The researchers specifically focused on how YouTube may assist students with analyzing various aspects of speech, such as contraction, speed, and tempo. Mayoral, P., et al (2010).

In summary, the previously mentioned research validates the effectiveness of social media in fostering the development of language abilities by providing real-world language resources, cooperative online environments, and chances for practice.

The Role of Social Media as Platforms for Communication between cultures *Socially practical Competence*

In order to get insight into the process of language learning, Hymes introduces the notion of interpersonal ability and asserts that, alongside linguistic rules, a thorough understanding of the principles governing acceptable language use is equally crucial Hymes, D. (1972). In essence, those who are acquiring a new language must possess the knowledge of "the appropriate timing and manner in which to express specific information to particular individuals" Larsen-Freeman, D., & Anderson, M. (2011). For educators to improve the communicative capacity of learners, it is crucial to cultivate socio-pragmatic abilities and use suitable language forms based on the specific context. From an anthropological standpoint, it is evident that every speech group has its unique set of speaking norms that are shaped by cultural and historical factors. In order to use language in a suitable manner, it is important for learners to familiarize themselves with the cultural standards associated with the target language Kaplan-Weinger, J., & Ullman, C. (2014). Numerous research have been conducted to investigate the impact of social media on the development of socio-pragmatic competence among language learners, considering different viewpoints.

In overall terms, prior empirical studies emphasize that social media platforms have shown effectiveness in enhancing socio-pragmatic competence. This is achieved by providing favorable opportunities for both receiving and producing language input.

Numerous scholars have emphasized the challenges associated with integrating socio-pragmatic instruction within conventional educational settings, where there is a scarcity of crucial elements such as genuine real-time feedback from individuals engaged in communication, contextualized situations, and dependable linguistic materials Kasper, G. (2001). And Blattner and Fiori (2011) postulated that social media platforms provide an interactive avenue for learners to engage with the target language community. Additionally, they argued that these platforms provide learners with genuine resources that facilitate socio-pragmatic learning, surpassing the constraints of physical distance and temporal limitations. In relation to this matter, the two researchers devised a Facebook initiative in which students are instructed to gather linguistic elements and do an analysis of speech actions pertaining to welcomes and farewells.

Facebook offers students the opportunity to engage with more complex and extensive language forms compared to conventional classroom settings. This exposure to many linguistic types provides students with valuable evidence for conducting thorough and meaningful studies of language use in different contexts. In the field of analysis, it has been seen that students demonstrate comprehension of formal as well as informal expressions of speech actions. Moreover, they make progress in identifying language rules that are exclusive to the context of Facebook. As a result, they develop an understanding of Facebook communications as a distinct genre Hanna, B. E., & de Nooy, J. (2003)

On the other hand, it may be challenging to perceive inside conventional educational settings.

A different component emphasizes social media as a source of stimulation for language output, since it provides learners with non-threatening environments in which they may experiment with and practice the language skills they have acquired. The pushed output theory, as proposed by Swain, M. (1985). mentions that students may only become aware of the discrepancy between their own production and the desired form of the target language by the act of producing language. This process eventually disrupts the existing representations in their interlanguage. Harting's research (2017). Aims to investigate the potential of Facebook as a tool for developing pragmatic competence among German learners. The study highlights Facebook's function as a platform for learners to actively engage in applying their pragmatic knowledge in real-life situations. The act of writing and exchanging postings with classmates has been shown to successfully engage learners in recognizing the subtle differences between expressions in the target language and their corresponding expressions in their home language. This practice also serves as a catalyst for learners to delve further into the cultural origins of these expressions In a similar vein, Reinhardt, J., & Ryu, J. (2013). have endeavored to

enhance the socio-pragmatic understanding of Korean learners via their utilization of Facebook as a platform. In summary, Facebook offers students a genuine communication situation in which they are required to generate suitable Korean honorifics for the respective identities of the individuals they are engaging with. Focusing on learner-generated texts, peers engaged in additional exploration and proofreading of the outputs based on the target phrases, in order to facilitate fresh observations and analysis. This approach has shown its effectiveness as students have typically exhibited an improved comprehension of contextual limitations on use and socio-pragmatic awareness.

Second Language Inspiration

The impact of social media on intercultural encounters has been generally recognized as a significant factor in improving the comprehension of socio-cultural aspects of the language being studied and fostering favorable attitudes towards language acquisition. In essence, these initiatives not only facilitate the development of intercultural competence, but also enhance desire for language acquisition. Motivation is often defined as "the inclination to initiate second language learning and the exertion of effort to maintain it" Ortega, L. (2009). Because of its significant role in the development of second language acquisition, there has been a substantial amount of work dedicated to exploring the correlation between social media and motivation for language learning. Consequently, many conceptualizations have emerged as a result of these investigations. One area of inquiry in language motivation study is on examining the effects of social media on learners' self-assurance in utilizing the target language. In their study, Lee and Lee use a quantitative approach to examine the potential correlation between virtual intercultural encounters and individuals' propensity to engage in communication. The findings indicate that virtual intercultural encounters have a positive impact on students' communication skills by facilitating interactions with individuals from varied linguistic backgrounds and enhancing their comprehension of the target language culture. With regards to the study findings, the authors further suggest that instructors have the ability to include language learners in activities facilitated by social media in order to enhance their understanding of multicultural experiences Lee, J. S., & Lee, K. (2020).

Another field of focus in motivation research is on exploring the possible impacts of social media on the development of one's future self-identification. Based on the L2 Motivational Self System, the concept of language learning motivation is often understood as the conscious endeavors undertaken by individuals in accordance with their future selves Dörnyei, Z. (2009). The correlation between social media and the formation of one's future self may be partially ascribed to the opportunity social media platforms provide for language learners to engage in low-risk social interactions, facilitating the building of transnational and cross-cultural identities Greenhow, C., & Lewin, C. (2016). This research investigates the relationship between social media use, motivated attempts in Chinese language acquisition, and self-identity evolutions among minority students in Hong Kong. Through the development

and examination of a structural equation model, the study supports the pathways connecting these variables. The research proposes that social media serves as a platform for individuals from cultural and linguistic minority groups to engage in the process of negotiating their identities. This negotiation involves the reconstruction of a dual cultural identity that encompasses both their own ethnic identity and their affiliation with the dominant mainstream society. Therefore, it is evident that the use of informal social media platforms has a significant role in enhancing learners' desire to acquire language skills. According to the research conducted by Lai Lai, C. (2019). it is argued that there is a need to separate social media users.

The study introduces an additional model that examines social media use from a nuanced viewpoint, distinguishing between passive and active social media behaviors. The differential is substantiated by the analysis of data, and the outcome affirms that diverse use of social media leads to distinct avenues for influencing motivation in language acquisition Lai, C., & Tai, C. P. (2021). When considering the use of social media as a language learning tool, it is crucial for language instructors and individuals from cultural or linguistic minority backgrounds to not only consider which platforms to use but also to carefully consider the strategies and methods employed in order to effectively assist language acquisition.

In the final analysis, the aforementioned empirical study demonstrates that social media has the ability to successfully enhance learners' motivation in acquiring a second language by facilitating positive emotional experiences and facilitating the development or reconstruction of their identities.

Constraints of Social Media Platforms

Social media platforms, despite their widespread popularity and influence, are not without their limitations. These constraints may hinder the effectiveness and reliability of social media as a means of communication and information dissemination. It is crucial While the advantages of incorporating social media into language instruction have been extensively examined, it is important to acknowledge that they are not without restrictions that need the attention of educators and learners. The identification of possible constraints and challenges associated with social media activities may assist educators and learners in mitigating the risks involved in using social media as instruments for language learning and teaching. The next section presents a summary of the identified constraints and provides ideas for improvement. Through an academic standpoint, it is important for both learners and educators to exercise critical thinking while using social media as a valuable source of information. This is because the linguistic resources obtained through social media platforms have the potential to introduce learners to contextually unsuitable or linguistically contradicting material. For example, the amalgamation of linguistic variances in the application of grammar and lexical knowledge is influenced by factors like as geographical places and personal styles. The term "repertoire" refers to a collection or range of skills, knowledge, or while many language variants may be advantageous for learners as they acknowledge and

appreciate diverse linguistic forms, others have the potential to cause confusion or errors. In relation to this matter, it is imperative for educators to provide essential assistance to learners in order to optimize the pedagogical benefits of genuine online resources. Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge that the cultural information disseminated via social media platforms may not be universally applicable in all contexts. In many contexts, a phrase that is deemed appropriate in one setting may be considered offensive in a different one. Consequently, it is important for learners to exercise careful consideration about the content they provide to social media platforms, as well as the information they consume from such platforms Haryanto, E., et al (2019).

From the standpoint of social media as a type of praxis, it is evident that social media platforms serve a multitude of purposes, including both professional and recreational domains. Consequently, it is imperative for students to exercise discernment and judiciously use these cutting-edge technologies. For instance, social networking platforms are equipped with captivating information and engaging features, which might potentially hinder learners' ability to concentrate on their educational pursuits. In their study on the integration of writing exercises into online social media platforms, Dirjal, A. H., et al identified instances when students may have challenges in remembering their online assignments and being sidetracked by other internet-related activities (p. 42). Furthermore, online correction checkers were first developed with the intention of improving the productivity and effectiveness of learners in their work and interactions. Nevertheless, an overreliance on online correction checkers might lead to a decline in spelling and grammatical proficiency Shih, R. C. (2011). Taking into consideration the possible constraints associated with social media in facilitating language acquisition, it is important for learners and educators to get guidance on the many capabilities offered by social media platforms. Additionally, regular contacts between teachers and students should be encouraged to monitor the progress of students and ensure they are making satisfactory advancements. By implementing the aforementioned measures, it is anticipated that the aforementioned issues will be mitigated or eliminated.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The rise and exponential expansion of social media has garnered significant interest from scholars in the field of second language acquisition. They have served as a catalyst for several research endeavors aimed at investigating the potential of social media as pedagogical instruments. Indeed, a growing corpus of research spanning several disciplines, viewpoints, and approaches has been undertaken, with valuable conclusions. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the effects of social media on language acquisition, with a particular focus on the use of social media as instruments for developing language skills and as venues for intercultural dialogue. The findings suggest that social media offers several advantages and serves various purposes in the language learning processes. These include the availability of genuine input materials, the provision of less anxiety-inducing practice

environments, a plethora of chances for intercultural dialogue, and the promotion of learner cooperation.

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